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**MENTAL HEALTH OF MEDICAL
STUDENTS**

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ABSTRACT:

Mental health, defined by the World Health Organization (WHO), is “a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to his or her community”. This cross-sectional study was conducted among medical students of different classes of different medical colleges. A predefined questionnaire was served. Different questions about name, age, gender, current class, residence (hostel or day scholar), food issues, mental stress of education etc. were asked. All the data was entered and analyzed using SPSS Ver. 23.0. A total of 90 medical students were included in this study. There were 45 (50%) male students and 45 (50%) female students. The mean age of the students was 21.22±2.21 years. Out of these 90 students, 75 were living in the hostels and the food quality of almost all the hostels was poor. Regarding the stress of studies, seventy percent of the students were stressed about their education and that they were suffering continuous pressure regarding this issue.

KEYWORDS: MENTAL HEALTH

INTRODUCTION:

Mental health, defined by the World Health Organization (WHO), is “a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to his or her community”. The three core components of this definition are (1) well-being, (2) effective functioning of an individual, and (3) effective functioning for a community. According to the WHO, mental health includes "subjective well-being, perceived self-efficacy, autonomy, competence, intergenerational dependence, and self-actualization of one's intellectual and emotional potential, among others". From the perspectives of positive psychology or of holism, mental health may include an individual's ability to enjoy life and to create a balance between life activities and efforts to achieve psychological resilience. Cultural

differences, subjective assessments, and competing professional theories all affect how one defines "mental health".

The absence of mental illness, however, is a minimal outcome from a psychological perspective on lifespan development. Corey M Keyes has created a two continua model of mental illness and health which holds that both are related, but distinct dimensions: one continuum indicates the presence or absence of mental health, the other the presence or absence of mental illness. For example, people with optimal mental health can also have a mental illness, and people who have no mental illness can also have poor mental health. Indeed, the World Health Organization distinguishes mental health from mental illness: a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity".

Marie Jahoda described six major, fundamental categories that can be used to categorize mentally healthy

individuals. These include a positive attitude towards the self, personal growth, integration, autonomy, a true perception of reality, and environmental mastery, which include adaptability and healthy interpersonal relationships.

Mental health problems may arise due to stress, loneliness, depression, anxiety, relationship problems, death of a loved one, suicidal thoughts, grief, addiction, ADHD, self-harm, various mood disorders, or other mental illnesses of varying degrees, as well as learning disabilities. Therapists, psychiatrists, psychologists, social workers, nurse practitioners, or family physicians can help manage mental illness with treatments such as therapy, counseling, or medication (1-3).

The purpose of this study was to see the status of mental health among medical students of different classes.

Material of Methods:

This cross-sectional study was conducted among medical students

of different classes of different medical colleges. A predefined questionnaire was served. Different questions about name, age, gender, current class, residence (hostel or day scholar), food issues, mental stress of education etc. were asked. All the data was entered and analyzed using SPSS Ver. 23.0. The qualitative variables were presented as numbers and frequencies. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

A total of 90 medical students were included in this study. There were 45 (50%) male students and 45 (50%) female students. The mean age of the students was 21.22 ± 2.21 years. Out of these 90 students, 75 were living in the hostels and the food quality of almost all the hostels was poor. Regarding the stress of studies, seventy percent of the students were stressed about their education and that they were suffering continuous pressure regarding this issue.

DISCUSSION:

Mental illnesses are more common than cancer, diabetes, or heart disease. Over 26 percent of all Americans over the age of 18 meet the criteria for having a mental illness. Evidence suggests that 450 million people worldwide have some mental illness. Major depression ranks fourth among the top 10 leading causes of disease worldwide. By 2029, mental illness is predicted to become the leading cause of disease worldwide. Women are more likely to have a mental illness than men. One million people commit suicide every year and 10 to 20 million attempt it. A World Health Organization (WHO) report estimates the global cost of mental illness at nearly \$2.5 trillion (two-thirds in indirect costs) in 2010, with a projected increase to over \$6 trillion by 2030.

Good mental health can improve life quality whereas poor mental health can worsen it. According to Richards,

Campania, & Muse-Burke, "There is growing evidence that is showing emotional abilities are associated with pro-social behaviors such as stress management and physical health." Their research also concluded that people who lack emotional expression are inclined to anti-social behaviors (e.g., drug and alcohol abuse, physical fights, vandalism), which reflects ones mental health and suppressed emotions. Adults and children who face mental illness may experience social stigma, which can exacerbate the issues. Mental health can be seen as an unstable continuum, where an individual's mental health may have many different possible values. Mental wellness is generally viewed as a positive attribute, even if the person does not have any diagnosed mental health condition. This definition of mental health highlights emotional well-being, the capacity to live a full and creative life, and the flexibility to deal with life's inevitable challenges. Some discussions are

formulated in terms of contentment or happiness. Many therapeutic systems and self-help books offer methods and philosophies espousing strategies and techniques vaunted as effective for further improving the mental wellness. Positive psychology is increasingly prominent in mental health (4-5).

REFERENCES:

1. Shin, Na Young; Lim, Young-Jin (December 2019). "Contribution of self-compassion to positive mental health among Korean university students". *International Journal of Psychology: Journal International de Psychologie*. 54 (6): 800–806. doi:10.1002/ijop.12527. ISSN 1464-066X. PMID 30206928.
2. "SEL: What Are the Core Competence Areas and Where are they Promoted?". casel.org. Retrieved 2020-11-14.
3. Department of Psychology, West University of Timisoara, Romania; Boncu, Alexandru; Costea, Iuliana; Department of Psychology, West University of Timisoara, Romania; Minulescu, Mihaela; National School of Political Studies and Public Administration, Bucharest, Romania (2017-12-31). "A meta-analytic study investigating the efficiency of socio-emotional learning programs on the development of children and adolescents"(PDF). Romanian

Journal of Applied Psychology: 35–41. doi:10.24913/rjap.19.2.02.

4. Goyal, Madhav; Singh, Sonal; Sibinga, Erica M. S.; Gould, Neda F.; Rowland-Seymour, Anastasia; Sharma, Ritu; Berger, Zackary; Sleicher, Dana; Maron, David D.; Shihab, Hasan M.; Ranasinghe, Padmini D.; Linn, Shauna; Saha, Shonali; Bass, Eric B.; Haythornthwaite, Jennifer A. (1 March 2014). "Meditation Programs for Psychological Stress and Well-being". *JAMA Internal Medicine*. 174 (3): 357–68. doi:10.1001/jamainternmed.2013.13018. PMC 4142584. PMID 24395196.
5. Galla, Brian M.; O'Reilly, Gillian A.; Kitil, M. Jennifer; Smalley, Susan L.; Black, David S. (September 2014). "Community-Based mindfulness program for disease prevention and health promotion: Targeting stress reduction". *American Journal of Health Promotion*. 30 (1): 36–41. doi:10.4278/ajhp.131107-QUAN-567. PMID 25162319. S2CID 503591.